

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

Adding New Datasets to the Human Reference Atlas Organ Gallery

Instructions for multiple file types and modalities

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Introduction

This Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) outlines the methodology for submitting new datasets for harmonization and visualization in the Human Reference Atlas Organ Gallery (Bueckle and Cyberinfrastructure for Network Science Center 2024) (Bueckle et al. 2023). It focuses on selecting data types and converting data into a usable format for visualization in virtual reality.

The primary audience for this SOP is collaborators who have 2-dimensional (2D) or 3-dimensional (3D) data that they would like to add to the HRA Organ Gallery. This SOP assumes basic working knowledge of Jupyter Notebooks (or a similar format, such as R Markdown), Python programming, and a basic understanding of 3D modeling using tools such as Blender (Blender Foundation, n.d.) and Unity (Unity, n.d.).

Roles and Responsibilities

The **Data Expert** is a collaborator who has 2D or 3D data.

The **Designer** creates and refines design specifications for virtual reality scenes based on discussions between Data Experts and the HRA Organ Gallery Lead.

The **HRA Organ Gallery Lead** oversees HRA Organ Gallery development and usage and serves as the primary contact for collaborators looking to view and explore their data in VR. The HRA Organ Gallery Lead makes decisions about technical specifications and is the primary point of contact for Data Experts.

The **Unity Developer** assists in processing collaborator data and they create, edit, and finalize scenes, levels, and interactions in the HRA Organ Gallery based on specifications provided by the Designer.

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Table 1. Roles, names, and email addresses of key personnel.

Role	Name	Email
Data Expert	various	various
Designer	Juhi Khare	jukhare@iu.edu
HRA Organ Gallery Lead	Andreas Bueckle	abueckle@iu.edu
Unity Developer	Yash Ramesh Kumar	yakuma@iu.edu

Procedures

Engaging with the HRA Organ Gallery team

- If not approached by the HRA Organ Gallery Lead first, Data Experts express interest in collaborating with the HRA Organ Gallery Lead via email, see address in **Table 1**.
- Data Experts determine what type of data is to be submitted, and convert it into one of the recommended formats detailed farther below in this SOP and in **Fig. 1**.
- If Data Experts are unable to convert the data or are encountering issues, they reach out to the HRA Organ Gallery Lead for assistance.
- Data Experts will be assigned a limited-access Google Drive folder by the HRA Organ Gallery Lead where they can upload files. Data will not be shared with anyone without the Data Expert's explicit permission, and will only be accessible to limited Organ Gallery team members working on data and models.
- They will also be assigned an Acknowledgements document, which is a Google document for providing relevant documentation regarding data they will have submitted. The document name will be of the format: "Effort-Biological Entity-Primary Investigator last name-10_power of ten." Unity Developers reference the information gathered in these documents to credit the Data Experts when their scene is ready for release, as well as to capture additional information about the collaboration. A template is provided in the appendix.
- The Data Expert fills in the required fields and specifies any special handling required regarding the data and metadata (method of extraction, age, sex, biological structure, etc.), and notes anything that needs to be mentioned in the scene for viewer reference.
- At any point, Data Experts are welcome to email the HRA Organ Gallery Lead or one of the Unity Developers assigned to their scene.

Formatting datasets and models for submission

To reliably submit data to the HRA Organ Gallery, collaborators must ensure that proposed datasets and models correspond to the correct format and, if they are 3D models, are within performance specifications (i.e., number of triangles/faces for provided models, see **Table 2**, for

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the HRA Organ Gallery. **Fig. 1** visualizes different input formats, workflows, and output formats with examples.

Figure 1. Input formats, workflows, and output formats with examples from the HRA Organ Gallery. These examples are named after the effort from which the data originates (e.g., “sennet”), the organ (e.g., “lymph-node”), the name(s) of the Data Expert(s), (e.g., “enninful-farzad”), and the level at which the data is shown (e.g., “10_2” denotes 10^2).

Adding cell location and annotation data extracted from PhenoCycler, Xenium, CyCIF (cyclic immunofluorescence), and other 2D or 3D datasets with segmented and annotated cells

- When submitting datasets with individual cells or other biological entities, such as RNA molecules, ensure the columns are of the form: x, y, (z), Cell Type/Biological Entity. The x/y coordinate and cell type columns are required while the z-coordinate is optional. A sample file is [available here](#). This is the same format used by the Cell Distance Explorer, see related paper (Jain et al. 2025).
- Preferred formats:
 - CSV
 - XLSX
- If the provided files are large, they can be compressed and provided as ZIP or GZ files.
- Additionally, AnnData ZARR (2D slice) formats must be converted to the aforementioned template format using Python. This makes it easier to visualize it in the [Cell Distance Explorer](#) (Jain et al. 2025), and in the HRA Organ Gallery (Unity).
- Fill out the Acknowledgements document, see the appendix for sample format. The HRA Organ Gallery Lead will share the correct document with the Data Expert.

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- Any special requests or additional information can also be included in the Acknowledgements document.

Adding mesh-based 3D models

- Ensure your submissions use one of the preferred formats:
 - FBX
 - OBJ
 - STL
 - GLTF/GLB
 - BLEND
- Alternative 3D model formats (pre-surface render) are possible:
 - SWC
 - OME-TIFF
 - OME-ZARR
 - AnnData ZARR (3D)
- AnnData ZARR (3D) file submissions are extracted for 3D coordinates, normalized, and have their surface reconstructed using Poisson reconstruction, using Python Scripts to output OBJ files which are then used in the HRA Organ Gallery (Unity). Requests to process AnnData submissions can be accommodated.
- Ensure submissions are within the triangle count permissible by Meta VR headsets as listed in the performance metrics, in **Table 2**.
- Data Experts are encouraged to convert their OME-TIFF and STL files to FBX or BLEND files using the Microscopy Nodes Add-on (Aafke Gros 2024) in Blender before submission, see below. Feel free to reach out to a Unity Developer for more information.

Table 2. Meta-recommended ranges for optimal triangle counts. Results may vary depending on various factors.

Platform	Triangle Count
Quest 1	350K-500K
Quest 2, Quest Pro	750K-1M
Quest 3, Quest 3S	1.3M-1.8M

Converting a OME-TIFF to a surface STL file

Perform the following steps in order.

- Note that when you install Fiji (ImageJ Wiki, n.d.), you need to make sure you have the correct Java version installed. See download instructions at <https://imagej.net/software/fiji/downloads>.
- Import OME-TIFF file into Fiji.

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- File > Open > Select file
- Imported OME-TIFF file opens in a new window with a slider to view slices
- Convert grayscale OME-TIFF to binary (make foreground and background visible).
 - Process > Binary > Make Binary > dialog box pops up
 - Retain the default settings
- Fill holes to prevent any internal gaps or holes within the binary objects to ensure the 3D model is solid without unwanted voids that could complicate surface generation.
 - Process > Binary > Fill Holes > Click OK to process all images
- Dilate to enlarge or expand the white areas (object pixels) which can help merge nearby pixels or close small gaps, making the object more continuous for better model integrity.
 - Process > Binary > Dilate > Click OK to process all images
- Use Erode to shrink or reduce the white areas, which removes stray pixels or noise introduced by dilation or scanning artifacts, cleaning up the binary object shape.
 - Process > Binary > Erode > Click OK to process all images
- Render the model using the 3D viewer plugin.
 - Plugins > 3D Viewer > Select OK
 - Renders Volume with a scale in a new ImageJ 3D viewer. 3D viewer render times may differ based on PC performance.
- In the ImageJ 3D Viewer, convert volume render to surface texture to make one singular mesh, and export as STL.
 - Edit > Display as > Surface
 - Your 3D render may disappear. This is because the model vertex definition has been rendered into a complete surface and there is no lighting in the viewer. This is completely fine and a desirable outcome.
 - File > Export surfaces > STL (ASCII for higher definition, binary for smaller file size+efficiency)

Converting a OME-ZARR to surface STL file

In [Blender](#):

- Refer to this [video](#) to install Microscopy Nodes Add-on. Edit drop-down menu > Preferences > Get Extensions > Search for “Microscopy Nodes” > Select Install.
- Press “a” (Select all in the scene), “x” (Delete), and “Delete” in the dialog box that pops up, to empty your Blender scene.
- Open Scene Properties > Microscopy Nodes tab
- In the TIF or ZARR” field, add your web URL/file location for the OME-ZARR file.
- Select desired scale to load the OME-ZARR file components, and desired pixel size.
- Choose whichever components are of interest in the inventory list below pixel size choice and select Surface option(s) for them.
- Click Load, and change Blender Render mode from Solid(default) to Material Preview”/”Rendered to visualize the newly loaded data.
- Make selection
- File > Export > STL/FBX/OBJ > Name > Save

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- Refer to [this video](#) for additional information when processing OME-ZARR files.

Converting to Unity usable FBX/OBJ format and further reducing the STL model with decimate modifier (optional)

In [Blender](#):

- Import STL file into Blender
 - File > Import > STL > Select file
- Apply Decimate Modifier: (optional)
 - Select imported object in Layout window
 - Modifiers > Decimate > Un-Subdivide tab > Iterate (0-6) as required
 - Apply modifier
- Export as FBX
 - Remove light and camera from scene hierarchy
 - Make selection
 - File > Export > FBX/OBJ > Name > Save

Reduce polygon count in MeshLab (“MeshLab - Download” 2025):

- Import mesh into [MeshLab](#).
 - Go to File > Import Mesh
 - Select your OBJ or STL file
- Check initial triangle count.
 - See bottom right of the MeshLab window to note the number of vertices and faces (triangles)
- Clean the mesh (optional but recommended).
 - Go to Filters > Cleaning and Repairing > Remove Duplicated Faces
 - Go to Filters > Cleaning and Repairing > Remove Duplicated Vertices
 - Go to Filters > Cleaning and Repairing > Remove Unused Vertices
 - Go to Filters > Cleaning and Repairing > Repair Non manifold edges (Fixes any topology issues)
- Reduce Triangle Count. This is a key step.
 - Go to Filters > Remeshing, Simplification and Reconstruction > Quadric Edge Collapse Decimation
 - Target number of faces: Enter the number of triangles you want (e.g., if you have 1 million faces, try 100,000 first)
 - Set the quality threshold between 0.5-1.0, starting with 0.7. Higher values preserve shape better but remove fewer triangles.
 - Check Preserve Boundary box
 - Check Preserve Normal box
 - Enable planar simplification if you have flat areas. It greatly improves triangle quality on planar portions.
 - Keep optimal position checked. This provides better quality. Click Apply.

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Adding Xenium transcripts

- Add datasets to the assigned folder in CSV or XLSX format or as a ZIP file.
- If the data has more than 1,048,576 rows (MS Excel upper limit), communicate this explicitly, as well as in the aforementioned Acknowledgements document, so that the data can be processed and cited correctly.
- Use the [Cell Distance Explorer](#) (Jain et al. 2025) to pre-visualize the dataset(s), and check whether the data provided is rendered correctly and accurately. To determine this, the Data Expert and/or the HRA Organ Gallery Lead can assess the number and types of cells shown and their spatial distribution. This will give a preview of how the data will look in the final scene.

Adding volumetric data: OME-ZARR scene setup

Figure 2. Full-resolution volumetric rendering of the OME-Zarr microscopy dataset (6001240.zarr) from [Blin et al. \(2019\)](#), displayed in Unity using a custom, GPU-based raymarching shader.

Figure 2 represents multiscale confocal microscopy data of a mouse blastocyst with simultaneous rendering of the DAPI and LaminB1 fluorescence channels. The MVP ingestion pipeline converted the original OME-Zarr dataset into Unity-compatible Texture3D assets with associated JSON metadata, enabling interactive volumetric visualization and channel compositing in a VR-compatible environment. **Left:** entire volume. **Right:** close-up. A GIF showing an interactive Unity/VR rendering of the mouse blastocyst OME-Zarr volume following implementation of runtime multi-channel compositing, anisotropic voxel correction, and URP-compatible volumetric rendering is available on [Google Drive](#). The scene supports immersive inspection through grab-and-scale interactions while preserving voxel spacing and multiresolution dataset structure derived from the original OME-Zarr hierarchy.

Reference Data Overview

The data is stored as a chunk, but has different levels defining resolution. Each level is made up of multiple channels that reference the same data, but at different definitions.

- The ZARR data store pyramid is designed to be accessed via scripts, and not meant to be viewed through a browser. It can be found [here](#).

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- This particular store (6001240.zarr) is a real OME-Zarr microscopy volume from the IDR (Image Data Resource), used widely as a reference NGFF dataset. It is a multiscale 3D fluorescence microscopy volume with two channels and explicit voxel metadata.
- The dataset is OME-Zarr v0.4 and contains:
 - 6001240.zarr/
 - 0 (full resolution)
 - 1 (2x downsampled)
 - 2 (4x downsampled)
 - .zattrs
 - .zgroup
- The axes are: (c, z, y, x), meaning c = fluorescence channel; z = depth slices; y/x = spatial image plane. There is no time dimension in this store.
- Voxel spacing at full-resolution level(0) is:
 - z = 0.5002 μm
 - y = 0.3604 μm
 - x = 0.3604 μm
 - Voxel spacing doubles each level in x/y.

Directions for replicating the scene above for use in future applications

Background information on the scene shown in **Figure 2**:

- A custom Unity Editor ingestion pipeline is used for converting exported microscopy volumes into native Texture3D assets and generates reusable dataset assets.
- A Python script then remotely accesses the publically available OME-ZARR datastore, and then locally stores it as RAW and JSON files pertaining to each of the channels per level.
- A JSON manifest is also built using the same script for Unity reference. GPU-based voxel volume rendering system is set-up in Unity using a custom HLSL raymarch shader, runtime multi-channel compositing, cube-based volumetric rendering bounds to obtain crisp and clear render of the volume, similar to Vitessce-style microscopy visualization workflows. Interactions such as Grab and Scale are added to make the ZARR Volume render interactable. The Universal Render Pipeline Build needs to be updated/amended so that ZARR volume is appropriately visible in the Quest Headset build.

Steps to replicate the scene in **Figure 2**:

- Use the Python script `export_omezarr_to_local.py` to directly ingest and validate OME-ZARR from an IDR microscopy dataset before saving to local storage as
 - `exported_volume/`
 - `manifest.json` (tells Unity how to read the files here)
 - `level_2` (RAW and JSON channel files inside)
 - `level_1` (RAW and JSON channel files inside)
 - `level_0` (RAW and JSON channel files inside)

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- Move the folder exported_volume/ inside the Unity project folder to the location Assets/Resources/.
- Next, use the editor script VolumeImporterWindow.cs from the menu option Tools>Volume Importer to utilize the newly imported ZARR store and convert it to a Unity usable dataset asset that will be used in another script to render the ZARR render. Set Assets/Resources/exported_volume/ as source folder, and another easily accessible folder as the destination folder, to obtain the following folder structure at the destination:
 - ImportedVolumes/
 - exported_volume/
 - exported_volume_Dataset.asset
 - tex_level0_c0
 - tex_level0_c1
- Next, create a material using VolumeRaymarch.shader, and attach it to the Mesh Renderer of a simple 3D cube in the Unity scene.
- Lastly, attach the VolumeRenderer.cs script to this cube, referencing the aforementioned dataset asset created by VolumeImporterWindow.cs editor script; the simple cube itself for the target renderer; and set Step Size: 0.001 along with Density: 1, adjusting for clarity of the ZARR render.
- A render of the ZARR volume inside the simple cube in the scene should be visible now.

Performance metrics

Data Experts and Unity Developers may find the following performance targets, provided by Meta, useful when creating model submissions. Hardware constraints limit the number of polygons or triangles to between 1.3M and 1.8M for Quest 3 headsets, as stated by Meta’s performance targets (“Testing and Performance Analysis,” n.d.) and represented in **Table 2**. Meta’s performance targets for call times are shown in **Table 3**. Data Experts may need to advise on downsampling rates for the whole dataset. For example, 10% of a high definition biological tissue unit that captures most of its hierarchical subunits is easier to visualize than the complete polygon-heavy model. The Data Expert and HRA Organ Gallery Lead need to collaborate to identify the appropriate level of detail.

Another metric to assess graphics requirements and performance are draw calls, which are commands sent by the CPU to the graphics card (GPU) to render an object, mesh, or material on the screen. A high number of draw calls can cause the CPU to bottleneck the GPU, which results in lower frames per second. Keep the number of draw calls within a range recommended by Meta.

Table 3. Sample draw call ranges.

Platform	Draw Calls	Description
Quest 1	50-150	Busy Simulation

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Quest 1	150-250	Medium Simulation
Quest 1	200-400	Light Simulation
Quest 2, Quest Pro	80-200	Busy Simulation
Quest 2, Quest Pro	200-300	Medium Simulation
Quest 2, Quest Pro	400-600	Light Simulation
Quest 3, Quest 3S	200-300	Busy Simulation
Quest 3, Quest 3S	400-600	Medium Simulation
Quest 3, Quest 3S	700-1000	Light Simulation

Definitions for Busy, Medium and Light Simulation, as described on Meta's official site ("Testing and Performance Analysis," n.d.).

- **Busy Simulation:** Applications with extensive simulations, VoIP, networking, animation, and skinning from other players or many NPCs. For example, multi-player shooters and populated social apps.
- **Medium Simulation:** Medium-sized worlds with fewer players or NPCs, such as single-player shooters and medium-populated social games. Most apps fall into this category.
- **Light Simulation:** Applications with minimal pipeline state changes such as escape room games, puzzle games, and co-op games.

References and Resources

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Glossary

3D model: Digital object with a shape and size defined by polygon meshes (vertices and edges) that can be used to represent the real-world form of anatomical structures, cells, or proteins in 3D.

comma-separated values (CSV): This is a text file that has a specific format which allows data to be saved in a table structure.

cyclic immunofluorescence (CyclIF) is a public-domain method for performing highly multiplexed immunofluorescence imaging using a conventional epifluorescence microscope. It uses simple reagents and existing antibodies to construct images with up to 30 channels by sequential 4- to 6-channel imaging followed by fluorophore inactivation.

Filmbox (FBX) file format: A proprietary file format (.fbx) developed by Kaydara and owned by Autodesk since 2006. It is used to provide interoperability between digital content creation applications.

GLB file format: Also called GL Transmission Format Binary file (.glb), this is a 3D file format specification, see <https://docs.fileformat.com/3d/glb>.

OBJ file format: Also called Wavefront Object file (.obj), this is a widely used, open-standard 3D file format that stores the geometry of 3D models—including vertex positions, faces, texture mapping coordinates, and normals—in a human-readable text format. OBJ files are compatible with most 3D modeling, printing, and visualization tools, and can reference material and texture data stored in associated .mtl files, but do not contain animation information.

Open Microscopy Environment Tagged Image File Format (OME-TIFF): A standardized image file format used in biological microscopy, which combines standard TIFF image data with embedded OME-XML metadata. TIFF is a flexible and widely supported raster image file format used for storing high-quality graphics, photographs, and scanned documents, often retaining rich color depth and lossless compression.

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PhenoCycler: This multiparameter imaging method, formerly known as CO-Detection by indEXing (CODEX), relies on oligonucleotide-conjugated antibodies and the cyclic addition and removal of complementary fluorescently labeled oligonucleotide probes. The commercial fluidics and high-plex image acquisition platform (Akoya Biosciences, Marlborough, MA) for this method enables whole slide imaging of up to 100 biomarkers on tissue samples in situ (Black et al. 2021; Goltsev et al. 2018; Kennedy-Darling et al. 2021).

stereolithography (STL): STL is a file format commonly used for 3D printing and computer-aided design (CAD). STL is also sometimes also referred to as Standard Triangle Language or Standard Tessellation Language. Each file is made up of a series of linked triangles that describe the surface geometry of a 3D model or object. The more complex the design, the more triangles used, and the higher the resolution.

Unity: A suite of software tools used to create interactive three-dimensional, two-dimensional, virtual reality, and augmented reality experiences.

voxel: A voxel is a small cube-shaped unit used to represent 3D space, similar to how a pixel represents a single point in a 2D image. The word comes from volume pixel. A voxel can be pictured as a block that stores information about a specific location in a 3D grid.

virtual reality (VR): a simulated three-dimensional environment that users can interact with in a seemingly physical and immersive way using specialized electronic equipment.

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Appendix: Acknowledgements Template

Title

Description

Size

Source

Notes

Screenshots

Video

Acknowledgments

Name, ORCID